

Synthesis and biological activity of some benzofuro[3,2-*d*]pyrimidines

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The condensation of ethyl 3-amino-2-benzofuran carboxylate (1) with phenyl isocyanate gave 3-phenylureido-2-benzofuran carboxylate (2), which upon treatment with phosphorus oxychloride gave 2-chloro-3-phenyl-3,4-dihydro-4-oxobenzofuro[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine (4). The reaction of 4 with alicyclic amines like piperidine and morpholine yielded 2-piperidino/morpholino compounds (5a and 5b, respectively). 2-Hydrazino-3-phenyl-3,4-dihydro-4-oxobenzofuro[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine (6) obtained from 4 was subjected to reactions with different reagents. All compounds were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities.

Naturally occurring benzofurans are associated with wide spectrum of biological activities¹. In continuation of our earlier work², several benzofuro[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine derivatives have been synthesized and screened for antimicrobial activities.

Results and discussion

The reaction of ethyl 3-amino-2-benzofuran carboxylate (1) with phenyl isocyanate in anhyd. pyridine at reflux temperature gave ethyl 3-phenylureido-2-benzofuran carboxylate

Scheme 1

late (**2**) (Scheme 1). Alternatively, the treatment of **1** with phenyl isocyanate in acetone at room temperature gave a compound identical to **2**. Under the same reaction condition, Dave *et al.*³ isolated the cyclized compound **3**. The reaction of **2** with freshly distilled phosphorus oxychloride at reflux temperature gave 2-chloro-3-phenyl-3,4-dihydro-4-oxobenzofuro[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine (**4**); probably both cyclization and halogenation occurred. Compounds **5a** and **5b** were obtained by the reaction of **4** with piperidine and morpholine in ethanol. The reaction of **4** with hydrazine hydrate in refluxing ethanol furnished **6**. The condensation of **6** with different aromatic aldehydes in methanol at room temperature led to the corresponding 2-arylideneamino-3-phenyl-3,4-dihydro-4-oxobenzofuro[3,2-*d*]pyrimidines (**7a-e**). The treatment of **6** with ethyl orthoformate gave a tetracyclic heterocycle **8**.

Antimicrobial activity : All compounds were screened against the bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* and fungus *Candida albicans* using DMF as solvent at 100 µg/ml concentration by cup-plate diffusion method⁴ using respectively gentamycin and griseofulvin as standard drugs. All the compounds showed moderate antimicrobial activities against all the organisms.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. IR spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Hitachi 270-50 spectrophotometer, ¹H NMR spectra (DMSO-*d*₆/CDCl₃) on a Bruker DR x 300 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a Jeol D-300 (EI) spectrometer. Purity of compounds was checked by TLC on silica gel-G plates.

3-Phenylureido-2-benzofuran carboxylate (2) : Method A : A mixture of ethyl 3-amino-2-benzofuran carboxylate (**1**; 0.01 mol) and phenyl isocyanate (0.01 mol) in pyridine (25 ml) was refluxed in an oil-bath for ~1 h. It was then cooled and poured in ice-cold water. The solid separated was dried and crystallized from dioxane. **Method B** : A mixture of ethyl 3-amino-2-benzofuran carboxylate (**1**; 0.01 mol) and phenyl isocyanate (0.01 mol) in dry acetone (20 ml) was kept at room temperature for ~48 h. The solid that separated was crystallized from acetone (80%), m.p. 216°; no depression in the m.m.p.; ν_{\max} 3320-3300 (NH), 1750 (C=O of carboxylic ester), 1660 cm⁻¹ (amide C=O); δ (DMSO-*d*₆) (3H, t, CH₃), 4.3 (2H, q, CH₂), 7-8 (m, ArH), 9.0 (1H, s, NH), 10.0 (1H, s, NH); *m/z* (%) 324 (M⁺, 49.8), 323 (100), 278 (30), 211 (65), 204 (55).

2-Chloro-3-phenyl-3,4-dihydro-4-oxobenzofuro[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine (4) : A mixture of freshly distilled phosphorus oxychloride (5 ml) and **2** (0.001 mol) was refluxed in an oil-bath for 3 h. After cooling, it was poured onto crushed ice with stirring. The solid separated was dried and crystallized from ethanol (78%), m.p. 139°; ν_{\max} 1710 (C=O), 1620 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ (CDCl₃) 7.07-8.0 (m, ArH); *m/z* (%) 296 (M⁺, 100), 298 (32.9), 262 (83.3), 205 (21.7), 130 (74.6).

2-Piperidino/morpholino-3-phenyl-3,4-dihydro-4-oxobenzofuro[3,2-*d*]pyrimidines (5a,b) : To a solution of **4** (0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml), piperidine/morpholine (0.02 mol) was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 h. The contents were then diluted with water and refrigerated overnight. The solids separated were dried and crystallized from ethanol : **5a** (50%), m.p. 184°; **b** (58%), m.p. 219°.

2-Hydrazino-3-phenyl-3,4-dihydro-4-oxobenzofuro[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine (6) : A mixture of **4** (0.005 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (80%; 0.01 mol) in ethanol (10 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The solid separated on cooling was crystallized from ethanol (60%), m.p. 178°; ν_{\max} 3380-3200 (NHNH₂), 1700 (C=O), 1600 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 5.8 (2H, s, NH₂), 7-8 (m, ArH), 8.78 (1H, s, NH); *m/z* (%) : 292 (M⁺, 42), 261 (100), 205 (14), 130 (76.3).

2-Arylideneamino-3-phenyl-3,4-dihydro-4-oxobenzofuro[3,2-*d*]pyrimidines (7a-e) : General procedure : To a solution of **6** (0.005 mol) in methanol (50 ml), aromatic aldehyde (0.005 mol) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 2 h. The resulting products were kept overnight. The solids separated were crystallized from ethanol (65-75%) : **7a**, m.p. 120°, **b**, 165°, **c**, 149°, **d**, 164°, **e**, 125°.

3-Phenyl[2,1-*b*]1,2,4-triazolopyrimido[4,5-*b*]benzofuran (8) : A suspension of **6** (0.0003 mol) in ethyl orthoformate (3 ml) was heated at 80° for 1 h. The solid separated upon cooling was crystallized from benzene (75%), m.p. 310° d; ν_{\max} 1670 (C=O), 1590 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 9.7 (1H, s, -CH=N-), 7.3-7.9 (m, ArH).

All compounds gave satisfactory N analyses.

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Note

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